

INCREASEMENT OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND FUNCTIONAL CAPABILITIES OF WRESTLERS

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Abstract. *This article aims to improve the physical fitness of wrestlers and increase the functional capabilities of wrestlers by developing general and special physical fitness (qualities). Physical fitness of a wrestler is one of the important components of sports training. Physical training is aimed at developing physical qualities, strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and speed. Physical training is divided into general, auxiliary and special training. The general physical fitness of a wrestler serves as a foundation, a basis for reaching a high level. The basis ensures the solution of the following tasks. Information about the comprehensive development of the body, increasing its functional capabilities, and developing its physical capabilities is given to wrestling.*

Keywords: *physical, morphological, psychophysiological, physical capacity, strength, endurance, flexibility, agility, speed, physical qualities, general physical fitness, functional capabilities, physical capabilities.*

Introduction. Today, the wide range of tasks being solved by wrestling specialists requires a more in-depth approach to the planning of wrestlers' training loads based on a comprehensive study of the methods and means of conducting sports training. These are the skills that distinguish the characteristics and qualities of an athlete that contribute more to achieving high sports results.

There are a number of works devoted to the experimental justification of the influence of physical, morphological and psychophysiological characteristics of wrestlers, individual typological characteristics of the nervous system, the nature of their attack movements, and their technique. Typography of muscle strength in wrestling depends on mobility of joints.

Many leading wrestling experts believe that a necessary condition for the success of competitive activities on the mat is to fight in a way that best suits the individual characteristics of the wrestler, and the training process should be designed considering their technical characteristics and a tactical arsenal.

Competitive activity has a great impact on the athlete's body. These are its extreme modes (maximum speed of individual movements and movements; maximum strength, endurance; complexity of coordinating movements with elements of danger, etc.) and neuro-emotional stress of stressful impact (social status of competitions, their opponents, etc.).

Physical qualities are usually called innate (genetically inherited) morphological and functional qualities, as a result of which it is possible for the physical (materially expressed) activity of a person to be fully manifested in the activity of the appropriate motor. The main physical qualities are muscle strength, speed, endurance, flexibility and agility.

The terms "development" and "education" are used in relation to the dynamics of changes in indicators of physical qualities. The term development describes the natural direction of changes in physical quality and the term education provides an active and directed influence on the growth of physical quality indicators. Modern literature uses the terms "physical qualities"

and "physical (motor) abilities". However, they are not the same. In general, motor skills can be understood as individual characteristics that determine the level of human motor skills.

These include: maintaining balance - on one leg, unstable support on it, after performing various rotations, etc. The main aspect of the development of a unique fighting skill is the learning and mastering of new technical movements, as well as the implementation of already known techniques and combinations.

General physical training includes a variety of tools. They include exercises performed without equipment and with equipment, exercises performed in special training with a partner, general developmental exercises taken from other sports: acrobatics, athletics, swimming, etc. Auxiliary physical training is necessary for effective performance of a large amount of work aimed at developing special movement skills designed to create a special basis.

Solves the following tasks with a specific direction:

- development of qualities that are more specific for wrestling;
- Selective development of the muscle groups involved in the actions of the wrestler.

As advanced means of auxiliary physical training, such exercises are used, which, according to their kinematic and dynamic order and the characteristics of neuromuscular tension, correspond to the main actions performed by the wrestler during the competition. Among such exercises, the following can be highlighted: execution of various methods of struggle by pointing; performing exercises on special training devices.

Literature analysis and methodology. The special physical training of the wrestler is aimed at developing the movement qualities of the wrestlers in strict accordance with the requirements imposed by the features of the competition. The basis of special physical training of wrestlers is conducted on the wrestling mat, and movement skills are aimed at developing the most important movement qualities in the experience. Therefore, various complex exercises, which are important as the main means of special physical training, are used in competition exercises. Such complex exercises increase the effect on the body of the wrestler. For example, choosing a partner in a heavier weight category, performing training competitions by changing partners, etc. All these exercises provide immunity to the development of one or another mechanism of energy supply and at the same time increase his physical and technical tactical readiness.

All the indicated types of physical training are interrelated. Inadequate assessment of any type of physical training during training will ultimately prevent the improvement of sports skills. Therefore, it is very important to observe the optimal ratio of the specified types of physical training during training. Its numerical expression is not considered a constant dimension, but the skills of wrestlers change depending on their individual characteristics, the period of the training process and the current state of the organism.

Cultivating strength. A wrestler's strength refers to his ability to overcome an opponent's resistance through muscle strength. By creating maximum muscle tension (muscle tension and relaxation), strength skills can be developed and improved. Therefore, the method of training strength is aimed at creating conditions for the muscles to fulfill the purpose in such cases. Most of the movement that a wrestler uses when he is directly facing an opponent is done in a quick-power or dynamic position. Holding with all your strength gradually or exerting without movement is understood as holding without changing the muscles or showing strength in the isometric mode. Thus, the nervous-muscular system of the wrestler should be ready for both

dynamic and static movement. During the competition, the ability of the muscles to show maximum force in a very short period of time is of particular importance, and it gives the wrestler an advantage over his opponent in the competition.

Famous wrestlers not only have a high level of development of physical training and a wealth of technical methods, but also are distinguished by the ability to show great strength at the right time. The results of numerous researchers show that it is possible to develop strength without significantly increasing muscle mass:

- in training aimed at developing strength without increasing muscle mass, it is necessary to work with as few repetitions as possible (1-3 times) with a large load and with increased rest intervals between movements;

- it is necessary to work with increased weight in exercises aimed at developing strength while gaining muscle mass.

- 50% of the load carried by the wrestler is repeated 8-10 times.

Analysis results. When we say the speed of a wrestler, we understand that he is able to perform certain actions in a short time, and when we say that the reaction of a wrestler is good, we understand that he performs captures or actions quickly and in a short time, defends and uses countermeasures. Making quick decisions depending on the situation, acting against the opponent's attack while training the quick action reaction. It is necessary to understand how to respond to his actions. Therefore, we mainly look at three types of reactions that occur in wrestling.

1. Simple reaction.
2. Complex reaction.
3. Selection reaction.

A simple reaction is to respond to a signal or sudden signal with a studied action. For example, the wrestler responds to the initiation of the technique with a prepared defensive or counter technique. Simple reaction time of an average wrestler corresponds to 220-260 ms / second. Several methods are used to train simple reaction speed. The most common of these is to react as quickly as possible to a sudden signal or change in the surrounding situation. We will dwell on two types of complex reaction speed, that is, the reaction to a moving object and the reaction of choice. The reaction to the object in motion is manifested in one-on-one acquisition exercises, for example, when a wrestler learns an action with a partner or a stick. Selection reaction consists in being able to choose one of the possible response actions according to changes in the opponent's behavior or the surrounding situation. For example, a defensive wrestler chooses one of the possible ways of defense depending on the way his opponent is attacking. The complexity of the selection reaction also depends on the rapid change of the situation. A wrestler's strength refers to the muscles of a wrestler who can withstand and defeat the opponent's moves. There are two main methods used to develop strength:

1. Dynamic exercises.
2. Static exercises.

1. Dynamic exercises are forces used to overcome movements. Dynamic exercises are forces used to overcome the motion or resistance of an opponent or heavy object. Dynamic exercises can be different:

- a) even if the load to be carried is not heavy, carry it out until exhaustion;
- b) perform a large load 1-3 times until exhaustion;

d) alternating, that is, starting with a small load, ending with an average and finally a large load.

For example, starting from one's own weight, adding weight to it, lifting it until it reaches strength (up to 60-90 kg.) or, if not, the opposite, i.e. 90 kg from a large size starting from, after 1-2 times lifting 60 kg weight until the muscles get tired.

2. Static exercises are temporary resistance to some force. Basically, the trainees have to hold a position on the barbell for a certain amount of time, such as standing in a corner position or lifting something heavier than themselves. In the development of strength, we mainly use exercises performed with weights. These are barbells, stones, dumbbells or your own weight. Exercises performed with a stone:

1. Lifting a stone from the chest with two hands.
2. Lifting a stone behind the head with two hands.
3. Sitting with a stone.
4. Putting the stone on the neck. turning the body while holding it with the hand.
5. Standing in the position of a bridge, lifting a stone with the help of hands.

The level of physical fitness of the athlete, physical qualities to achieve high sports results; development of strength, speed, flexibility, endurance, agility is of primary importance. That is why physical training, which is carried out together with the process of improving the fighting technique, plays a leading role in the process training. Physical training requires the necessary reconstruction of all physiological functions in the body. in general, it ensures the harmonious development of the whole organism. Depending on the nature of physical exercises and the methods of their application, three types of changes can occur in the body:

1. Mutual cooperation.
2. Neutral.
3. On the contrary, it is a situation that interferes with each other.

If the first one is obtained in the exercise complex, this is a positive effect of the exercises. If the third occurs, the negative effects of exercise. In this regard, the role of choosing the right sources of physical training is also important in GPT. "General Physical Training" (GPT). The main task of GPT should be to develop speed, strength, agility, flexibility and endurance. These situations mastered with the help of GPT are considered the main ones in their development, considering the nature of sports wrestling. Walking, running, swimming, sports games, comprehensive gymnastics exercises are the source of GPT. Correct tanking of the GPT exercise contributes to the physical development of the wrestler. A wrestler must be able to run, jump, climb a rope, play sports, lift weights, perform complex acrobatic exercises, and more. In these types, the wrestler does not have to achieve high sports results. Because all these exercises are considered practical (they can be used in exercises other than sports). GPT continuously expands the athlete's functional capacity, allows to increase the load, and helps to increase the results.

"Special Physical Training" (SPT). The special physical training of a wrestler is aimed at the development of physical qualities in the performance of actions typical for wrestling. It is also used as a component of the entire training process at all stages of the competition period. Exercises related to the acquisition and improvement of technique, as well as the study and improvement of competitions in various directions are considered a source of SPT. In most cases, special exercises express certain elements of technique or method, which the wrestler

performs independently or with another athlete. The advantage of special exercises is that they help the wrestler master the wrestling technique while solving the SPT task. Speed up. A fighter's speed is his ability to perform certain actions in a short period of time. If we are talking about the speed of the wrestler, ideally, we want the wrestler to spend the least amount of time to react, quickly catch the opponent and apply a technique or use defensive and counter attack moves. The speed feature can be divided into two main groups. One of them is the speed of different forms of movement reaction, and the second is the different form of speed of movement. The speed of movement reaction is important for fighting. It includes the time from when a signal is given (perceived by sight, hearing, or tactile sense) to the initiation of a response action.

Simple and complex movement reaction times vary (from 0.15 seconds to 0.5 seconds). Reaction speed is important not only in the defensive and counter-attacking actions of the wrestler, but also in the actions related to the attack. In defense and counter-attack, the wrestler observes a threatening movement, and this movement of the opponent is a signal to which he must respond. The position of the opponent or his movement, which creates good conditions for the attack, is a signal for the wrestler. Thus, most of the actions of the wrestlers in the competition will have the character of a response reaction against a certain reaction.

Summary. Physical fitness of a wrestler is one of the important components of sports training. Such preparations are aimed at developing physical qualities of strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and speed. The main tasks of physical training are as follows: increasing the level of health of athletes and the functional capabilities of various systems of their bodies; development of physical qualities in a unit that meets the unique characteristics of a wrestler.

Physical training is divided into general and auxiliary, special training: General physical training of a wrestler: it serves as a foundation and basis for reaching a higher level. The basis ensures the solution of the following tasks: all-round development of the organism for combat, increasing its functional capabilities, developing its physical capabilities; improve health; proper use of active rest during intense training and competition loads.

It can be said that the speed of the movement reaction occurs in every movement of the wrestler, regardless of whether the movement is in the spirit of defense, counterattack or attack. does not pay attention, the question may arise as to what the speed of movement reactions depends on. Apparently, in addition to the personal characteristics of the wrestler and the state of his sports form, it is also necessary to consider the relationship with his level of practical experience. For example, avoiding the eye depends on the fighter understanding the danger that the opponent's movement or behavior poses at the moment and being able to use them to attack.

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